

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 9, No. 5; May 28, 2003

Dear Readers:

In April we have had a special issue on "Dynamic Symbolic Languages": if you have not done so already, maybe you want to have a look at it! It is accessible as "sample issue" also for those who do not yet subscribe to J.UCS, so please make sure to also point friends and colleagues to it, to further increase the impact of our journal.

This May issue in front of you is sandwiched between the just mentioned special issue and the June issue dedicated to Knowledge Management, a spin-off of the highly successful conference on Knowledge Management that takes place every year in Graz at the beginning of July, see http://www.know-center.tugraz.at/en/conference/i-know03/iknow03_home.htm Thus, you will be happy to see that the May issue is slim, for a change, but contains two very nice papers that I hope you will enjoy reading!

Let me wish all on the Northern Hemisphere a good summer, and a not-too-cold winter to those down under!

Cheers,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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